

ENSURING FLUENCY IN SPEECH IN INITIAL EDUCATION READING COMPREHENSION LESSONS

¹Mukhitdinova Kh.S., ²Omanov P.H., ³Nasriddinova N.A.

¹Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

²Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) on Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor, Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

³Teacher at the Department of "Primary Education Methods", Gulistan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13144686>

Abstract. *The process of globalization is leading to the expansion of socio-economic and socio-political-cultural interactions among countries, thereby increasing the demand and importance of developing communication culture in language education. Language education aims to develop students' speaking skills from an early age through forming their conversational skills, which are fundamental tasks for improving their speech culture. Improving students' pronunciation of speech sounds in their native language, as well as their writing and reading skills, starting from the early grades, is one of the key factors in ensuring language proficiency and fluency, contributing to the development of students' communicative competencies and speech culture. Nowadays, under international research methods such as PIRLS, particular attention has been paid to improving students' reading proficiency from the early grades. In this article, the results of experimental work on improving reading speed with respect to pronunciation proficiency in developing students' reading proficiency are presented. Teaching reading proficiency in lessons involves teaching students to correctly pronounce speech sounds, improve reading speed, pay attention to the placement of emphasis during reading, intonation, and fluency, teaching the skill of reading fluently without unnecessary pauses - all of these elements together form a speech technique. Starting from the early stages of education, teaching speech techniques by shaping pronunciation of speech sounds, words, and sentences to improve reading fluency helps students reach speech fluency. The article emphasizes the importance of providing reading through learning, ensuring that the speed of reading does not lag behind comprehension of sentences and text content, and the importance of progressing through the text at a pace that aligns with understanding the text quickly.*

Keywords: *language teaching, initial education, speech culture, reading proficiency, correct pronunciation, speech speed, speech fluency, developing speaking skills, speech technique, teaching through reading, understanding text, research results.*

Introduction

Speech is a particular form of social activity of language, carrying out the need for individuals to express their own thoughts and exchange ideas. Within the process of speech, each unit of language serves the specific function of expressing a certain meaning or carrying out an expressive task. In the organization of speech, phonetic, lexical, and syntactic units are interrelated in terms of mutual relevance and articulate syntagmatic and paradigmatic relationships. In this complex process, the correct pronunciation of speech sounds and the accurate differentiation in writing, reading without additional repetition maintaining the speed of speech, placing stress correctly in the reading process, paying attention to intonation patterns are the key elements in shaping students' speech fluency, and all these together form the technique of speech.

Improving speech techniques ensures the fluency of speech and opens up the path to the culture and art of speech. In this case, the importance of the mother tongue is extremely significant, precisely the teachings of the mother tongue and reading comprehension help students avoid various grammatical mistakes and teach them to use language units correctly. These initial classes also emphasize the importance of the mother tongue in the teaching methodology [1].

General lower secondary schools underline the development of students' speech culture and fluency in the Uzbek language in continuous education stages according to the State educational standards [2], paying particular attention to developing speech activities - listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. Shaping reading comprehension skills in the teaching of the mother tongue is considered the core foundation of developing speech proficiency, and shaping these skills correctly from the very beginning classes ensures the fluency of students' speech and contributes to the development of their speech competencies. If we consider the enhancement of students' reading skills through the reading of texts they study in other subjects, contributing to their logical and creative thinking, and the development of the ability to apply acquired knowledge in life as important aspects of their development nowadays, shaping students' reading skills is ultimately one of the urgent issues.

Recognizing letters, reading words based on letters, understanding their meanings enhances the child's thinking and helps them generalize what they know, develop the ability to learn what they don't know through reading. The broadening process of understanding new information unknown to them through reading enhances students' thinking, scope, and content. As it is seen, literacy is not just recognizing letters, adding letters and reading words, but rather the quality of developing thinking through speech activities in its entirety. The unity of language and thinking is the key point here, where the significance of reading activities is crucial.

Activity is a psychological process, and in Q. Turgunov's "Dictionary of Psychology Terms in Russian-Uzbek," the word "activity" is explained as "the form in which a person's relationships with reality emerge" [3, 45]. In psychological research, 3 main types of activity are identified: work activity, learning activity, and play activities. According to A.G. Mukhiddinov, any activity is carried out based on effective motives and is shaped by the person's goals, worldview, interests, needs, tendencies, as well as knowledge, skills, and habits [4, 4.] Speech activity is also carried out based on effective motives and cognitive processes - understanding, communication, are closely related. Thus, the integrative interrelation of speech activity types in both psychological and linguistic didactic perspectives has been studied, particularly by M. Gulyamova in her research, where integration in education is described as the synthesis of knowledge, skills, and attitudes formed on the basis of various subjects as well as the development of speech activity types in mutual interconnection and complexity [5, 23.]

From the stated ideas, it can be emphasized that learning activity is directly related to understanding and communication activities, and when it comes to generating conclusions, these activity types are perceived as products of interdependence. Therefore, literacy is not just about recognizing and reading simple letters, but also about understanding what is read, interpreting meanings, and acquiring knowledge. On the other hand, the direct connection of the comprehension activity with the articulation activity implies that while the learning activity is strengthened by the practice of writing simultaneously, reading is not just a sign of understanding, but also a means to develop speech activity.

Reading is deriving knowledge, becoming literate. The process of recognizing letters and words, as our great thinker Alisher Navoiy put it, transforms a person's existence to the better, refines their thinking, and liberates them from the animal world. Due to this, every person will always remember their teacher from the initial grades who activated their understanding, and by mastering literacy, reading a series of books, their speech will develop, expanding their vocabulary. The quality of these processes, the direct link to literacy activities, and all of this being part of language and literacy education classes are crucial for all subjects.

Literacy classes, along with broadening vocabulary, also aim to shape students' speech technique and gradually enhance their understanding and reading skills, directing them towards the goals of reading and understanding, i.e., comprehension of what is read. The process of forming words from letters simultaneously with shaping speech technique in language and literacy education classes highlights the emphasis on creating short texts of 2-3 sentences containing educational important phrases linked to subsequent sentences. This way, the child gradually learns when to say what and how to act in certain situations.

In the following, reading is not just learning letters, adding them to form words and thereby shaping children's speech, but also providing broad opportunities for shaping contemplation, walking, sitting, observing the rules of self-control in society, emphasizing national spiritual values and shaping world perception. Reading comprehension lessons simultaneously teach children how to read and write, as well as give them vital life skills: the child connects his spoken words and sentences he has read to the society, shapes social relationships, changes his attitude towards family, living and non-living nature, understands the necessity for others to live in society, learns how to apply the content of conversations to life. Through these lessons, children learn to communicate with people, how to speak correctly, how to speak incorrectly, the oral and written rules of language: correct pronunciation, putting the emphasis correctly, forming words and understanding the rules of correct usage, as well as making effective use of language tools. Reading comprehension lessons focused on developing conversational skills are a pedagogical process aimed at developing speaking skills, which by their nature ensure that learners acquire effective conversation skills using appropriate methods, techniques, and tools, guiding the learners in this process by identifying necessary cues in critical areas. In this case, understanding certain standards in the tempo of speech, in the speed of reading words is also important, beyond excessively slow or quick reading, it is possible to miss the meaning of words and sentences. Therefore, starting from the initial grades and teaching correct pronunciation through teaching, shaping children's speech technique through improving reading fluency is considered one of the necessary conditions for providing reading comprehension.

PRIMARY SECTION THE LEVEL OF ORGANIZATION AND INTEGRITY OF THE PROBLEM.

The main goal of ensuring students' literacy in the initial education is to develop their oral and written speech, to cultivate speech culture through teaching literary speech standards. Based on this goal, the curriculum of the subject "Native language and reading literacy" includes: 1. Teaching literacy and speech development. 2. Phonetics, grammar, spelling, and speech development are covered in the structural parts [6, 3-20]. According to the schedule, literacy training is divided into readiness and alphabet periods, and two learning sessions are conducted. In these lessons, students learn to express sounds in writing with letters, form words from letters, learn to read correctly, as well as separate words into syllables, syllables into sounds, and articulate

sounds in words. Beginning with the letter "O," students who take the first step into school are taught to read and write 29 letters. However, in order to develop practical reading skills, in addition to reading and writing the letters of the alphabet in the 1st grade, forming words from vowels and consonants, articulating sounds, and combining them into words are paid attention to, meaning that word formation from these letters is demonstrated, and reading exercises are carried out in the context of word structure. This demonstrative method helps to form the skill of word formation, to move from the word method to the sentence method of understanding and generalizing concepts. Thus, through literacy training in this way, students' speech is developed with the ability to read words and sentences accurately, fluently, articulately, and comprehensively, and their understanding of the environment is also expanded. During this period, the practical analytical-synthetic method of forming correct pronunciation is used to improve children's phonemic perception abilities. In grades 1-2, students are provided with concepts related to sound and letter, the basic and small forms of letters, vowels and consonants, their graphic representation, articulation, consonant, voiced and voiceless consonants, and practical skills and abilities are developed in students. In general, shaping students' reading literacy through literacy training not only teaches them oral speech, correct pronunciation, and writing skills but also teaches them to think in speech. First, reading and writing are taught to the child who steps into the school gate. Knowing how to read and write is considered the sign that the child's education has begun. Reading activities are actually carried out in all subjects in the early grades, but teaching reading and understanding the meanings of words being read is the main task of native language lessons [7, 145].

The curriculum "Mother Tongue and Literacy" was created in collaboration with the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) for initial grade students [8, 317]. It is recommended that, starting from the middle of the academic year, the development of literacy skills should be emphasized. In the early grades, it is suggested to allocate 8-10 minutes of each mother tongue lesson to literacy exercises. Among the literacy exercises, particular attention should be paid to not neglecting the value of letters, the height and width measurements, avoiding errors such as distorting the shape or writing, as well as addressing other difficulties specific to individual handwriting. In addition, some students are given individual exercises to overcome such difficulties through one-on-one sessions. Providing examples of writing and regularly checking the notebooks of all students in grades 1-2, along with exercises to help develop beautiful and proficient writing, is recommended to strengthen the knowledge gained in mother tongue studies [6, 3-20].

Furthermore, in the early grades, mother tongue activities focus on improving students' oral and written speech through reading, writing, and learning grammar material. In research activities, it is possible to observe the study of literary pronunciation and its norms in the developed countries' languages, based on world experience, including the beneficial use of phonetic exercises in the English language. Detailed information is provided about the process of producing each speech sound in English language textbooks and teaching materials widely used in various countries [9, 7].

METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING SPEECH COMPETENCE.

In the initial grades, teaching reading and writing is carried out simultaneously. In the first grade, during the second quarter, children are taught words that differ in pronunciation and spelling

when spoken and written; the pronunciation and spelling of homophones; even if the homophones without a difference in pronunciation are heard without a pair of homophones at the end of the word, they are written with a pair; the disappearance of some sounds at the end of certain words in pronunciation but their retention in writing; understanding the pronunciation and writing of homographs with different meanings; learning to represent sounds with letters, to form words from letters and sounds, to correctly structure words and phrases in writing, to listen and write words and short phrases without a difference in pronunciation and writing; recognizing the first word of a sentence, people's names, place names, and the names of certain animals written with capital letters. In this way, both oral and written speech competence is developed.

The initial curriculum is structured on the basis of modularity and activity orientation, and basic information provided by phonetics, grammar, and spelling is complemented by grammatical materials taught in higher grades. In grades 3 and 4, knowledge related to sounds and letters is consolidated, tasks related to sounds and letters are performed to improve and enhance the oral and written language culture of young students. For each topic in the textbook, words, phrases, and texts are selected with special attention to the students' level of knowledge and age characteristics. The scope of topics widens from grade to grade in the initial curriculum. Specifically, in the 4th grade curriculum, a significant part of the reading lessons focuses on reading comprehension and working with the text, paying special attention to expressive reading and understanding what has been read.

The State Educational Standards outline the requirements for the subject "Mother Tongue and Reading Literacy" for initial classes in general education schools, aiming to ensure students' literacy in the initial stages of education. These standards emphasize the formation of students' literacy by teaching them to understand the teacher's speech, simple texts, and assignments within the framework of reading topics; to participate in conversation with the teacher based on illustrations and read texts; to use newly learned words in oral speech during the speech process. The teaching period for literacy spans from September 2 to the end of December, covering the last months of the academic year. The literacy teaching process is structured from preparatory and alphabet periods, where students in the first grade learn to read the letters O, N, A, I, M, T, L, B, K, R, O', D, U, Y, E, G, Ng, S, H, Sh, P, Q, Ch, J, G', Z, V, X, F, forming complex words, reading fluently and expressively in accordance with the intonation of the sentence, as well as meeting the requirements of reading small poems given by the topic; reading short dialogic texts with correct intonation. According to the State Educational Standards, in the preparatory and alphabet period, literacy teaching is carried out using analytical-synthetic (analytic-synthetic) sound methods. According to the analytical-synthetic method of literacy teaching, analysis is carried out from text to speech, speech to word, word to syllable and sound, or vice versa, sound > syllable > word > speech > text, in a sequential and interconnected manner. In the initial stage of literacy teaching, special attention is paid to expanding students' vocabulary, which contributes to the development of their thinking activity based on the principles of didactics, clarity, and logic.

From the second half of the 2nd grade, the development of phonetic skills continues. In the initial grades, it is recommended to allocate 8-10 minutes of each mother tongue lesson to phonetic exercises. Group activities are also conducted with some students to correct shortcomings related to phonetics (such as insufficient attention to letter pronunciation, incorrect height and width measurements, breaking the shape when writing, etc.), as well as other errors specific to each student's handwriting. Individual and group exercises are conducted to correct these errors.

Continuous monitoring and evaluation are one of the educational conditions ensuring the consolidation of knowledge acquired from mother tongue lessons. Various types of written tasks, such as dictation, educational, explanatory, illustrative, dictionary, creative, free dictation, as well as educational presentations and essays, are used to identify how students have internalized the knowledge learned from mother tongue lessons.

The practical application of our mother tongue as the state language, as well as increasing its influence and use, requires a significant amount of work to be done in this field. Our research during the process revealed the following deficiencies in students' proficiency during lesson observation in initial grades:

Among 1st-grade pupils:

- Struggling with reading fluently, reading letters individually but unable to combine them into words;

- Incomplete recognition of letters;
- Reading words but not understanding their meanings;
- Not paying attention to additional marks in words and not reading fully until the end;
- Reading quickly and making mistakes;
- Putting marks for unknown words because dictionary work has not been done;
- Cases of skipping unfamiliar letters within words.

Among 2nd-grade pupils:

- Struggling with both letter and fluent reading;

- Struggling with pronunciation of open syllable words that come in the middle or at the end of a sentence;

- Confusing the positions of letters B and D;
- Having difficulty in correctly pronouncing and writing letters X and H;
- Difficulty in recognizing and placing letters I, -L, -ib, -di, -iq, -ib, -Q, -B;
- Difficulty in correctly placing the accent and struggling with fluent reading.

Among 3rd-grade pupils:

- Incomplete recognition of all letters, inability to say the correct word based on recognized letters;

- Not understanding the content of the read sentences;
- In the listening process, not fully understanding the meanings of words and sentences;
- Not fully understanding the content of the text during reading.

Among 4th-grade pupils:

- Not being able to understand the content of the read text and repeat it;
- Understanding the teacher's spoken words, but not what they have read themselves;
- Ignoring some additional elements in word compositions during reading;
- Making errors like leaving out some additional elements while writing.

RESULTS OF THE STUDY OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF READING. During our research, experiments were conducted on determining the reading speed of students using the method recommended by the methodologist R. Shomahmudova in grades 1-2 through the game "Know Yourself" [11, 79]. The purpose outlined in this game was to determine how many words students could read within a certain time frame, and initially, students were asked who would like to be the "mover" in this game. One of the volunteered students is taken to the board. Other students in the class show the words written on cards to the student who becomes the "mover". The "mover"

student must read these words correctly. After each word, the "mover" points to the next word as a sign. If the student reads the word incorrectly, they are replaced, and the role of "mover" is given to another student. This game helps students to improve their attention, speed, and reading comprehension. In grades 3-4, the level of formation of reading habits through teaching early and folk tales was also observed in terms of the speed of reading and the level of formation of reading skills through reading texts. The results obtained in the course of these experiments aimed at determining the reading speed were as follows in the boundaries and sections of classes:

In the Sirdaryo region, the reading speed of students in grades 1-4 [12] is as follows:

Classes	How many words read in one minute	
	(highest)	(lowest)
Grade 1	66	5
Grade 2	68	6
Grade 3	135	15
Grade 4	153	7

In the Jizzakh region, the reading speed of students in grades 1-4 [13] is as follows:

Classes	How many words read in one minute	
	(highest)	(lowest)
Grade 1	112	12
Grade 2	98	13
Grade 3	119	9
Grade 4	117	69

Reading speed of students in grades 1-4 in the Ulug'bek district of Tashkent city [14].

Classes	How many words read in one minute	
	(highest)	(lowest)
Grade 1	89	11
Grade 2	102	24
Grade 3	119	30
Grade 4	123	46

In the analysis of speech rate in the experimental section, it was shown that in the 1st grade, the highest indicator of speech rate was 112 words, in the 2nd grade - 102 words, in the 3rd grade - 135 words, and in the 4th grade - 153 words, forming a sentence. The lowest indicator of speech rate, however, was in the 1st grade with 5 words, in the 2nd grade with 6 words, in the 3rd grade with 9 words, and in the 4th grade with 7 words forming a sentence.

It was observed that some students read too quickly, while others read too slowly. During fast reading, students made errors such as not pronouncing certain sounds correctly, skipping some additions in words, ignoring word stress, and not paying serious attention to the intonation and rhythm of speech. Conversely, during slow reading, errors such as not being able to add letters to form words, hesitating or stumbling over words, struggling to read fluently, placing stresses incorrectly, and not understanding the meaning of words or the content of the read sentences

properly occurred due to the violation of speech techniques. The disruption of speech fluency ultimately leads to the lack of development of comprehension skills.

According to the curriculum approved in 2005 [12, 31], during the 1st half-year of the 1st grade, the reading rate is 20-25 words (with the reading speed of the explanatory text also being 20-25 words); at the end of the academic year, it is 20-30 words; during the 1st half-year of the 2nd grade, the reading speed is 30-35 words; during the 2nd half-year, it is 40-50 words; during the 1st half-year of the 3rd grade, it is 60-70 words; during the 2nd half-year, it is 70-80 words; during the 1st half-year of the 4th grade, it is indicated as 110-130 words without voice, and with voice, it is 90-100 words. In the State Educational Standards of December 17, 2021, only for 4th grades, the normative level is set at 50-55 words at level A1 and 55-60 words at level A1+.

In today's perspective, correct pronunciation of speech sounds in accordance with the current State educational standards and our national curriculum, as well as paying broad attention to adding intonation patterns while reading, have been emphasized. However, the pace of reading assigned to this normative document, the speed of reading words, and adding intonations (later additions) to speech to ensure fluency in speech have not been addressed. It is known that the Uzbek language belongs to the agglutinative language group. This structure plays a significant role in the grammatical structure of languages, and additional elements are added to the word stem. As a result, sentences with 4-5 clauses (sometimes even more) emerge. This naturally leads to a decrease in the speed of reading words, occasional pauses in oral speech, and in some cases, even the omission of certain sounds, and the distortion of intonation patterns. Overcoming these challenges requires consistent work on speech speed and fluency starting from initial classes. Unfortunately, in the development of today's reading technique, the issue of reading speed is not given due attention. As noted, this issue is not even separately specified in the State educational standards requirements. Fast reading should be understood as reading at a pace consistent with understanding the content of the text, where reading speed should correspond to the speed of understanding the text. If speed negatively affects the comprehension of the content, this criterion is not considered. This situation indicates how challenging the issue of reading is in the initial classes of general education schools. Reading speed varies for different students, of course. Experiments show that a child may grasp 200 words out of a 250-word text in a minute. If a child reads word by word or phrase by phrase, their attention is not focused on words but on phrases, resulting in them being unable to grasp the words. If these criteria are applied to 4th-grade students, it is evident that out of 125 words, a child may understand 100 words. At the same time, our observations also show that there are students in the 4th grade who can read 170—180 words in a minute. However, as mentioned above, this does not guarantee the understanding of all words.

Our analysis indicated the following as the main reasons for students making errors in their reading:

1. Because of the lack of accurate synthesis between pronunciation and understanding the meaning of words, students often focus on the sound aspect of a word rather than comprehending its meaning, leading to errors in pronunciation.

2. Complex words, especially those not encountered in childhood, can lead to errors in pronunciation.

3. Errors occur due to a lack of understanding of the meaning of words.

4. Rushing through the text can result in errors.

5. Proper reading is also dependent on adequate lighting and visibility.

6. Students struggle with reading sentences that contain open-ended words interspersed between closed-ended ones at the beginning, middle, or end of a sentence.

To address reading errors, attention should be given to the following factors:

1. Pre-teaching challenging words and practicing reading by segmenting complex words into syllables before teaching the text.

2. Familiarizing students with the lexical meaning of words that may obscure understanding of the text's content before reading.

3. Creating conditions conducive to attentive reading.

4. Teaching orally first, then having students read aloud.

5. Taking into account students' individual characteristics in teaching, identifying students who find the text easy, moderately difficult, or challenging, and allocating tasks accordingly.

6. Regularly monitoring students' correct reading.

7. Identifying the appropriate methodological approach based on the nature of the error.

8. Anticipating potential error-prone areas and providing explanations in advance.

9. Identifying potential error-prone areas and providing explanations in advance.

10. Considering the influence of a student's personal perception on reading errors.

By writing complex words with syllable divisions beforehand on the board and practicing reading aloud with students, they can effectively improve the correct pronunciation of the words, the rhythm of speech, and the intonation of sentences, thus helping children listen and practice according to the standard form of sounds, intonation, and sentence patterns contained in these words. Good reading is considered the fundamental quality of good reading. Reading involves understanding the exact content, the author's implicit direction, images, and the role of literary means, as well as expressing one's attitude towards the events described in the text. Reading also depends on students' essential life experiences, understanding the lexical meaning of words, the connection of words in sentences, and a series of methodological conditions. Students are required to correctly perceive and understand the text in order to read it smoothly. In many cases, the analysis of the content of the text from the perspective of literary means is carried out to help students understand the text better.

Conclusion

The need to shape the reading skill of interpreting experimental works that have been studied emphasizes the necessity of implementing it gradually. In this regard, it is important not to rush in shaping the skills at the initial stage, but to pay attention directly to correct comprehension. In subsequent stages, shaping the ability to connect paragraphs to each other gradually accelerates, thereby forming the skill of reading experimental works in a coherent manner. This contributes to ensuring fluency in speech. Increasing the speed of reading during the reading process also contributes to the formation of the skill of interpreting. Therefore, as emphasized by D.A. Leontiev, the method of reading by reading word combinations and sentences, small texts, does not yield results in the reading process [14, 13-46].

Reading speed gradually increases over ten years in direct relation to correct and effective reading. Increasing the speed of reading allows children to simultaneously comprehend and memorize texts, remember articles, practice reading aloud, that is, teaching children through reading. When checking reading speed, the teacher should take into account the complexity of the text to be read, the structure of words and sentences, the degree of their use in children's speech, and the correctness and fluency of reading.

Thus, in language education, reading is considered a major tool for shaping correct pronunciation and speaking skills, as well as performing many tasks for writing. Exactly at the initial stage of education, teaching students to correctly read aloud, to form words by connecting speech sounds to each other, and to teach reading fluently without accents with clean pronunciation create conditions for mastering the language. Reading helps to internalize new words and expand vocabulary, as well as develop skills in combining words into sentences and forming sentences and paragraphs. Reading and getting acquainted with nature and society not only enriches a child's knowledge but also develops speech and thinking. The ability to generalize what one knows and to learn what one does not know through reading begins to emerge.

Therefore, drawing conclusions, literacy is not just about recognizing letters, not just about recognizing letters and combining them into words by reading aloud, but also about developing the quality of a person's speech activity and thinking through the meaning of the word as a whole. Shaping literacy in mother tongue education is considered the basis for developing speech literacy, and these skills should be shaped correctly from the very beginning of classes, ensuring the fluency of students' speech and contributing to the development of their speech competencies.

REFERENCES

1. Teshaboyev D. R., Khamdamova R. E. Methodology of teaching mother tongue in the initial grades of general secondary schools / J. EJAR. - No. 7. - 2020. – 823 p.
2. General Secondary Education State Educational Standards
3. Turgunov Q. Dictionary of Psychological Terms in Russian-Uzbek. – Tashkent: Teacher, 1975. – 45 p.
4. Mukhiddinov A.G. Speech Activity in the Learning Process. – Tashkent: Teacher, 1975. – 4 p.
5. Gulyamova M. Kh. Integrative Approach to Developing Communicative Competence in Teaching English: Ped. Sci. PhD dissertation. – Tashkent, 2018. – 23 p.
6. Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Republican Educational Center for General Education. General Education Curriculum (Grade III).- Tashkent, 2018.- Pages 3-20.- 29 p.
7. Mukhitdinova Kh.S. Scientific and Methodological Foundations of Teaching Uzbek Language (monograph). - Tashkent, 2020. - 145 p.
8. Mamatova G., Baynazarova O., Goziyeva D., Haydarova F., and others. Mother Tongue and Reading Literacy (textbook). – Tashkent. 2022. - 317 p.
9. Bonk N. A., Kotiy G. A., Lukyanova N. A. English Language Textbook. – Moscow: Dekont, 1999. – P.7.
10. General Secondary Education State Educational Standards and Curriculum. Initial Education. – Tashkent, RTM. – 2017.- Page 31.
11. Shomakhmudova R. Teaching Correct Pronunciation and Speech Development. Methodical Guide for Auxiliary Schools. Revised and Reissued 20th edition. - Tashkent- Ilm Ziyoy, 2013.- 79 p.
12. Reference letter from the Syrdarya Region. Head of the RTM Donaboyev Otabek Mamatqulovich. Schools 54-47. 10.10.2022.
13. Reference letter from the Jizzakh Region. Head of the RTM Sadriddinova Dilfuza Roziqulovna. Schools 19-21. 17.10.2022.

14. Reference letter from the Mirzo Ulugbek district of Tashkent city. Head of the RTM Sh.A. Ikramov. Schools 148-205. 17.10.2022.
15. General Secondary Education State Educational Standards and Curriculum. Initial Education. – Tashkent: RTM. – 2005. – Page 31.
16. Umarov H., Turdiyeva R., Nasriddinova N. Methodology of Teaching Mother Tongue. Educational Methodological Collection: Guliston - 2020. - Pages 44-45. (194 p.)
17. Leontiev D.A. Self-actualization as a Driving Force of Personal Development: Historical-Critical Analysis // Contemporary Motivational Psychology. - Moscow, 2002. - P.13-46.